

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Perceived Relationship between Utilisation of Serial Resources and Research Productivity of Postgraduate Students in Private University Libraries in North Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated perceived utilisation of serial resources by postgraduate students in university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. Three objectives which were to identify the types of serial resources utilised by postgraduate students, determine factors influencing research productivity, and determine perceived relationship between utilisation of serial resources and research productivity guided the study. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The sample was 234 postgraduate students from selected universities in North Central, Nigeria were used due to its manageable size. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled “Perceived Relationship between Utilisation of Serial Resources and Research Productivity of Postgraduate Students in Private University Libraries in North Central, Nigeria Questionnaire (PRUSRRPQ)”. The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Library and Information Science, while a pilot study produced a Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficient above 0.80. Data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation. Postgraduate students utilised various serials such as journals, abstracts and indexes, conference proceedings, theses, annual reports, e-book collections, and newspapers. The study revealed that serials are used by postgraduate students. The findings also established a strong perceived relationship as serials enhanced research quality, publication output, collaboration, efficiency, and academic visibility. The conclusion was that effective utilisation of serial resources significantly contribute to improved research productivity of postgraduate students in private universities in North Central, Nigeria. The recommendation is that private universities should provide adequate and current serial resources, improve ICT facilities, and organise information literacy programs to enhance effective utilisation of serial resources for improved research productivity.

Keywords: Postgraduate Students, Private University, Utilization, Serial Resources, Research, Research Productivity.

1. Introduction

University libraries according to Ekere, Omekwu and Nwoha (2016), play significant role in supporting teaching, learning, and research activities in higher institutions through a wide range of information resources that assist students, lecturers, and researchers in achieving academic objectives. Among these resources, journals, conference proceedings, magazines, newspapers, abstracts, indexes, and electronic databases are highly important because they contain current and specialized information. He highlighted that serial resources contribute significantly to academic research because it provides researchers with updated findings and professional discussions in different disciplines. Postgraduate students depend largely on serial resources for advanced academic investigations, literature reviews, and scholarly research activities. The availability and effective utilization of these resources contribute greatly to academic excellence and knowledge development in universities.

Furthermore, Ani (2016) stated that the rapid advancement of ICT has transformed the way serial resources are accessed and utilized in university libraries. Electronic journals, online databases, institutional repositories, and digital library platforms now provide users with easier and faster access to scholarly information. He pointed that ICT-based library resources have

improved accessibility and utilization of scholarly information among researchers and students, and also observed that electronic information resources have enhanced postgraduate students' access to academic materials and increased the effectiveness of research activities in Nigerian universities. Through these, postgraduate students are able to access recent findings, deepen their understanding of research topics, and improve the quality of their scholarly work.

According to Abouchedid and Abdelnour (2015), research productivity remains one of the major indicators of academic performance and scholarly contribution in higher institutions. Postgraduate students are expected to contribute to knowledge through theses, dissertations, journal articles, conference papers, and other scholarly outputs. They averred that research productivity reflects the intellectual contribution of scholars and institutions to knowledge development. Abramo, D'Angelo and Murgia (2017) also opined that access to quality research resources contributes positively to research productivity and scholarly collaboration. Consequently, university libraries are expected to provide adequate serial resources capable of supporting the research needs of postgraduate students.

Despite the importance of serial resources, several challenges continue to affect their

effective utilisation in many university libraries. Inadequate funding, high subscription costs of journals, poor ICT infrastructure, insufficient awareness of available resources often limit utilization of serial resources by postgraduates. Ani (2016) observed that inadequate availability and accessibility of information resources constitute major challenges affecting effective library utilization in Nigerian universities. Similarly, Yushau and Fadipe (2018) also highlighted that poor ICT facilities and unstable internet services negatively affect effective utilization of electronic resources in universities. These challenges may negatively affect research productivity and reduce scholarly outputs. The study sought to investigate perceived relationship between utilisation of serials by postgraduate students in university libraries in North Central, Nigeria.

1.1 Statement of Problem

Universities generally provide current and relevant resources for teaching, learning, and research. Serial resources remain essential for postgraduate students because they provide recent scholarly information necessary for academic investigation and research productivity. However, many students appear to experience difficulties such as inadequate awareness of available resources, poor ICT facilities, insufficient information literacy skills, and limited access to current serial publications have continued to hinder effective utilisation of serial resources. As a result, many postgraduate

students may experience difficulties in producing quality research output and achieving satisfactory scholarly productivity.

Efforts aimed at improving utilisation of serial resources in university libraries have not fully addressed these challenges due to inadequate funding, poor ICT infrastructure, and irregular updating of library collections. Consequently, postgraduate students may continue to face limitations in accessing current and relevant scholarly materials needed for effective research activities which may contribute to low research visibility, weak academic output, and reduced scholarly contribution within private universities. These therefore justify the need for the study on perceived relationship between utilisation of serial resources by postgraduate students in private university libraries.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The study sought to investigate perceived relationship between utilisation of serial resources and research productivity of postgraduate students in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Identify types of serial resources utilised in private universities in North Central, Nigeria.
2. Determine the factors influencing research productivity in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria.

3. Determine perceived utilisation of serial resources for research productivity by postgraduate students in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria

2. Literature Review

This section reviewed related literature relevant to the study.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the Uses and Gratifications Theory, developed by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch in 1973. The theory explains how individuals actively seek and utilize information resources to satisfy their specific needs and achieve desired goals. The central theme of the theory is that users of information are participants that consciously select information sources that best meet their academic, professional, and personal needs.

The relevance of the Uses and Gratifications Theory to this study lies in its ability to explain how postgraduate students actively utilise serial resources to satisfy their research and academic information needs. Through journals, electronic databases, conference proceedings, and other serial publications, postgraduate students seek current and reliable information that can improve the quality of their research productivity. This provides a framework for motivations behind utilisation of serial resources and how it contributes to research effectiveness, academic performance, and scholarly output.

Applying the Uses and Gratifications Theory to this study helps to explain utilisation of serials by postgraduate students in university libraries. It further underscores how serials are effectively utilised, which determines the level of satisfaction, research competence, and scholarly productivity achieved in their academic pursuits.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The concepts are anchored on six key concepts central to understanding perceived relationship between utilisation of serial resources and research productivity of postgraduate students in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. These are: Postgraduate Students, Private University Libraries, Utilisation, Serial Resources, Research, and Research Productivity. Each concept is discussed to provide a clearer understanding of the variables that guide the study.

2.2.1 Postgraduate Students

According to Akpe, Chukwuka and Salisu ((2019), postgraduate students are individuals who have completed undergraduate education and are pursuing advanced academic programs such as postgraduate diploma, master's degree, and doctoral degree. They represent a unique category of university library users because of the intensive research demands associated with their academic programs. Postgraduate students engage more actively in research-oriented academic activities than undergraduate students

because of the advanced nature of their programs. Unlike undergraduate students whose studies are largely classroom-oriented, postgraduate students engage more deeply in independent learning, critical analysis, and scholarly investigations. Postgraduate students are involved in extensive reading, literature reviews, data collection, analysis of scholarly materials, and preparation of theses, dissertations, seminar papers, and journal articles. Promise and Kikiri (2023) also averred that postgraduate students perceive serial resources as important tools for academic success and scholarly investigations. These categories of students require access to current, relevant, and specialized information resources capable of supporting high-level academic work. Consequently, they spend considerable time consulting serial resources such as journals, conference proceedings, research reports, and electronic databases.

Similarly, Moustapha (2022) argued that postgraduate students contribute significantly to knowledge generation and research productivity within universities. Through their research projects and scholarly publications, they contribute to innovation, academic growth, and societal development. He stated that access to serial publications improves the quality and quantity of scholarly outputs among university researchers. Their research is hinged on the accessibility of information resources available to them. With adequate resources, postgraduate

students are capable of contributing meaningfully to academic discourse and national development. However, challenges of library resources, ICT, and limited access to current serial publications may affect their ability to fully utilize available serials. University becomes pertinent in supporting them through orientation and user education programs.

2.2.2 Private University Libraries

Private university libraries according to Akindele (2014) are those established within privately owned universities. They support research activities by serving as information centres responsible for acquiring, organizing, preserving resources to students, lecturers, researchers, and other members of the community. They were established to complement public universities in improving academic development. Effectiveness of private libraries is measured by what they provide to support academic programs and research activities. Private university libraries provide electronic resources that support academic needs of users. Their collections typically include textbooks, journals, newspapers, magazines, conference proceedings, theses, dissertations, reference materials, and electronic databases. Similarly, Weber and Flatley (2018) averred that electronic resources have become important components of modern academic library collections because they improve accessibility and convenience for users. These resources are essential for postgraduate

students who require current and specialized information for advanced research activities.

Aside the provision of access to information resources, private university libraries also offer services such as reference services, user education programs, information literacy training, indexing and abstracting services, and access to electronic databases. In addition, Hjørland (2000) highlighted that library and information services are fundamental to effective knowledge organization and dissemination in academic environments. Furthermore, Ekere, Omekwu and Nwoha (2016) opined that users' perception of library services influences the extent of resource utilization in university libraries. These services are intended to assist users in locating and utilizing relevant information effectively. Many private university libraries face challenges that affect their ability to provide adequate information resources and services. In addition, Muftahu (2021) observed that many private higher institutions in Nigeria face infrastructural and funding deficits affecting educational development. He argued that inadequate funding and poor acquisition policies contribute to shortages in current library resources in Nigeria which include inadequate funding, high subscription costs of journals, poor ICT infrastructure, unstable internet connectivity, insufficient professional staff, and irregular updating of library collections, which negatively affect the research productivity of postgraduate students. Consequently, the

effectiveness of private university libraries largely determines how postgraduates successfully utilize serials for academic research.

2.2.3 Utilisation

According to Ani (2016), utilisation is the effective and practical use of resources to satisfy specific academic, research, or personal information needs. In the library context, utilization involves use, access, availability of resources for learning, teaching, and research activities. He argued that utilization is the practical application of available resources for achieving organizational and academic objectives. Similarly, Afebende and Ebanye (2018) observed that library resource utilization serves as indicator of effective library collections and services. Utilisation is considered one of the major indicators of the effectiveness of library collections and services because resources can only achieve their purpose when they are actively used by users. Utilisation of library resources involves activities such as searching library catalogues, consulting journals and databases, borrowing materials, downloading electronic resources, reading scholarly publications, and applying retrieved information to research activities. They also observed that students who effectively utilize library resources demonstrate improved academic engagement and learning outcomes.

Furthermore, Nutsupkui and Owusu-Ansah (2017) averred that several factors influence

utilisation of library resources of postgraduate students. These include availability, accessibility, awareness, ICT skills, relevance of materials, internet connectivity, and quality of library services. They also observed that awareness significantly influences users' utilisation of serial resources in academic libraries. They also highlighted that accessibility determines postgraduate students' use of library. Similarly, Ifijeh and Ogbomo (2018) averred that effective utilisation contributes positively to university users. Postgraduate students who effectively utilize serials enhance critical thinking, improved understanding of research topics, and support evidence-based academic writing.

2.2.4 Serial Resources

According to Moustapha (2022), serial resources are materials issued in successive parts and intended to continue indefinitely. These include conference proceedings, indexes, abstracts, and electronic databases. In academic libraries, serials are highly valued because they provide current and up-to-date information across different fields of study. They are essential components of university library collections because they support teaching, learning, and research activities. In addition, Usman and Batagarawa (2023) averred that serial resources enhance effective information utilisation among academic library users. Unlike textbooks that may become outdated after some years, serial publications frequently provide recent findings,

emerging trends, and current scholarly discussions. Serials are useful for postgraduate students who require recent information for literature reviews, data analysis, and scholarly investigations.

Furthermore, Kananzawa (2020) argued that ICT facilities format has transformed accessibility of serial resources. He observed that electronic serial materials have significantly improved management of resources by enabling users to retrieve scholarly materials remotely and conveniently. Despite the importance of serial resources, challenges include: high subscription costs, inadequate funding, poor internet connectivity, irregular updating of collections, and limited access to electronic databases. Nevertheless, serial resources remain fundamental to academic research because they provide reliable and current information necessary for quality scholarly productivity.

2.2.5 Research

According to Adikwu, Aduloju and Emaikwu (2019), research is a systematic and thorough investigation or inquiry into a subject or topic to discover, interpret, or revise facts, theories, or applications. Research aims to answer or solve problems, explore new ideas or phenomena, test hypotheses or theories, develop new concepts or frameworks, advance knowledge and understanding. Research in library and information science according to Ifijeh and Ogbomo (2018) is a systematic investigation of

issues relating to practice and education to increase the sum of knowledge in the field. In addition, research helps to address real-world problems, pushes boundaries in various fields, and enhances the institution's reputation. Research is therefore an investigation to determine facts in order to know whether the facts should be retained as satisfactory status quo or they need some amendments.

Research productivity according to Abouchedid and Abdelnour (2015) refer to scholarly publications by individuals, groups, or institutions within a specific period. This involves the generation and dissemination of new knowledge through writing theses, dissertations, journal articles, conference papers, books, technical reports, and other scholarly publications. They averred that research productivity refers to academic performance, intellectual contribution, and institutional development. Research productivity is an important aspect of academic success for postgraduate students because their programs are largely research-oriented. They are expected to conduct independent investigations, contribute to knowledge in their fields of study, and produce scholarly works capable of addressing societal and academic problems. The quality of research productivity of postgraduate students depends largely on access to adequate information resources, effective supervision, research skills, and availability of current scholarly materials.

In addition, Abramo, D'Angelo, and Murgia (2017) argued that research productivity contributes significantly to academic growth, innovation, and national development. They observed that increased access to serial resources enhances the quality of research output and academic visibility of researchers. Furthermore, Bala, Isah and Ibrahim (2023) opined that serial resources utilisation contributes positively to collaboration, publication output, and scholarly productivity which help in advancing scientific discoveries, and improving educational standards. Consequently, universities place strong emphasis on promoting research culture and providing adequate support systems that can improve scholarly productivity. Factors like access to information resources, utilisation of serials, ICT facilities, funding, research competence, and institutional support influence research productivity. Similarly, Fawzi and Al-Hattami (2017) averred that institutional support and access to information resources positively affect research performance of postgraduate students. Effective utilisation of serial resources particularly plays a major role in enhancing research productivity because it provides access to current and authoritative information needed for quality academic investigations. With available serial resources, postgraduate students produce relevant, reliable, and impactful scholarly outputs.

2.3 Related Empirical Studies

In a research study by Shaba, Owoeye and Jimoh (2024) to investigate the accessibility and use of serial publications for academic activities in federal universities in North Central, Nigeria. Objectives of the study were to find out extent of use of serial publications. 136 copies of questionnaire were administered, while 121 were analysed. Descriptive statistical tool of frequency counts and percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the data. Both studies are related because they discuss use of serial publications for academic activities. The former is on Library and Information Science Educators (LISE) in federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The present was on utilisation of serial resources and research productivity in private universities in North Central, Nigeria. Both studies adopted a survey research design and questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. Geographically, both studies were carried out in North Central, Nigeria although they focused on different target populations and academic contexts. The former study was limited to two objectives and two research questions involving Library and Information Science Educators, while the present is broader, covering three objectives which include research productivity. The sample size differs, with 136 respondents in the former and 234 in the present. Both studies employed descriptive statistical tools of frequency counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation for

data analysis. The gap identified is that no similar study on serials by postgraduate students in university libraries has been conducted in North Central, Nigeria.

Promise and Kikiri (2023) investigated utilisation of serial resources and sampled 295 postgraduate students. Questionnaire was the instrument of data collection. The findings showed a positive perception on the use of serial resources as they are essential for researchers and students and contain facts and figures needed for research. Serials present various ideals on a variety of subjects. The finding noted that journals, theses and dissertations were the main serial resources most frequently used. Challenges encountered include lack of borrowing facilities or journals in my area, poor searching abilities, unstable power supply, lack of manpower to effectively handle customer requests, and outdated periodicals. Descriptive survey research design and Questionnaire as the instrument of data collection were used. Findings suggested measures for overcoming the challenges including poor funding for the library. Both studies investigated perceptions and utilisation of serial materials in the East, two state and two federal universities. Both studies focused on postgraduate students' perceptions and utilization of serial resources in university libraries. The present study was carried out in private universities in North Central, Nigeria and also includes productivity. Methodologically, both studies adopted survey/descriptive survey

research design and used questionnaire for data collection, though both differed in sample size (295 in the former study and 234 in the present study). The gap identified is that no similar study has been conducted on postgraduate students' utilisation of serials and research productivity in North Central, Nigeria.

A study conducted by Olutoki and Osoba (2017) on how serial collections are utilized. 1,464 respondents were sampled out of which 146 were chosen. The present study sampled 234 respondents. The instrument used for data collection was research questionnaire. Findings revealed that newspapers were the most consulted. There was no mention of sampling techniques. Both studies examined the use of serial resources in academic libraries, although in different institutional and geographical settings. While the earlier study focused on selected tertiary institutions in Ogun State, the present study was conducted in North Central, Nigeria and includes productivity. Both studies used survey research design and questionnaire for data collection, but differ in sample size and scope. The gap addressed by the present study is the absence of similar research in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria.

3. Methodology

The survey research design was considered appropriate because it enabled postgraduate students' serial resources and research productivity without manipulating any variables.

Seven private university libraries were selected as the setting with 234 postgraduate students (PGD, Master's, and Ph.D) across the universities. The private universities and their student population are: Al-Hikmah University (32), Bingham University (50), Karl Kumm University (12), New Gate University (23), Nile University (57), Salem University (28), and University of Mkar (32). The universities were selected using cluster sampling method based on location, size and year established, but within each university, census sampling was adopted. The sample size for the study was 234, arrived at during the pilot testing stage. The justification for this is that no previous study was ever carried out in the zone. Since the population was manageable, the entire population was invited to participate without applying any sampling technique. A structured questionnaire titled "Perceived Relationship between Utilisation of Serial Resources and Research Productivity of Postgraduate Students in Private University Libraries in North Central, Nigeria Questionnaire (PRUSRRPQ)" was used. The instrument was validated and necessary corrections were made before final administration. A pilot test involving 31 postgraduate students from Greenfield University, Kaduna produced a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient above 0.80, confirming the instrument's reliability. Questionnaire was administered by trained assistants, 234 copies giving a 100% response rate which was achieved at the pilot testing stage. According to Emaikwu (2019), when a

population is relatively small the entire population can be used for the study. This was achieved through the use of institutional authority because each postgraduate student was expected to compulsorily register in the university library to keep record of the total number of students in any given academic session. Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 26). Means and standard deviations were calculated for all questionnaire items. Decision rule of 2.50 was the benchmark for mean interpretation. This study adhered to ethical research practices. Institutional approval was obtained, and all participants provided informed consent. Anonymity and confidentiality were guaranteed throughout the data collection and analysis process.

4. Result

Table 1 presents the Mean and Standard Deviation of Types of Serial Resources Utilised in Private University Libraries in North Central, Nigeria shows that all eight categories of serial resources: journals, abstracts, theses, conference proceedings, transactions of societies, annual reports, e-book collections and newspapers are consistently available across all seven selected private universities (Al-Hikmah University, Bingham University, Karl Kumm University, New Gate University, Nile University, Salem University, and University of Mkar). The findings of this objective reveal that private universities in North Central, Nigeria utilise a

wide range of serial resources. All the resources recorded mean scores above the criterion mean, indicating general agreement that they are actively used. Abstracts and indexes, journals, and conference proceedings were the most utilised, while newspapers recorded the lowest usage, though still within the accepted range. This could be due to lack of time on the part of the postgraduate students. The findings align with the study by Shaba, Owoeye and Jimoh (2024), which reported that serial publications are widely used. This shows a consistent pattern across studies that serial resources remain essential academic tools, regardless of institutional type or location.

Table 2 presents the Mean and Standard Deviation of Factors Influencing Research Productivity in Private University Libraries in North Central, Nigeria. The findings indicate that all indicators, including access to resources, funding, institutional support, research output, research skills, publications, and collaboration, recorded mean scores within the high-level range. Research funding was the strongest factor influencing productivity, while publication output and collaboration opportunities were relatively lower but still high. The findings align with Shaba, Owoeye and Jimoh (2024) who stated that serial resources enhance academic reliable information needed for research. The present study extends the literature by clearly showing that serial resource use is not only high

but also positively associated with research performance of postgraduate students.

Table 3 presents the Mean and Standard Deviation of Perceived Relationship between Utilisation of Serial Resources and Research Productivity of Postgraduate Students in Private University Libraries in North Central, Nigeria. The results of this objective show a perceived positive relationship between serial resource utilisation and research productivity. All items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean, indicating agreement that serial resources improve research quality, output, collaboration, efficiency, publication rate, and academic visibility. The highest-rated perception was that serial resources enhance research productivity, confirming the findings align with Shaba, Owoeye and Jimoh (2024) who stated that serial resources are critical for producing quality research outputs and improving academic performance.

5. Discussion

Table 1 revealed that postgraduate students agreed that journals, abstracts, thesis, conference proceedings, transactions of societies, annual reports, e-book collections, and newspapers were the types of serial resources available for utilisation of postgraduate students in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. The result showed there is significant positive relationship between available serial resources for utilisation of postgraduate students in North

Central, Nigeria. The study aligns with Egbe (2016) who stated that access to e-resources like Ebscohost and Science Direct provided access to serial resources for effective research productivity.

Table 2 also revealed that access to resources, conference presentations, number of publications, funding, and institutional support were the factors influencing research productivity of postgraduate students in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. The finding aligns with the study by Bala, Isah and Ibrahim (2023) who stated that funding, mentorship, institutional support and research collaboration influence research productivity. The finding is also in tandem with the study by Abouchedid and Abdelnour (2015) who stated that creating a research culture that appreciates research and institutional support can enhance research productivity.

Table 3 further revealed that the perceived relationship between utilisation of serial resources and research productivity of postgraduate students in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria is said to be strong, because majority of the students agreed that use of serial resources leads to improved research quality, enhanced research productivity, greater research output, and collaboration. The study aligns with that by Akpe, Chukwuka and Salisu (2019) who stated that non-utilisation of serial resources leads to low level of research

productivity of postgraduate students in academic libraries in Nigeria.

6. Conclusion

The findings of this study concluded that utilisation of serial resources plays a significant and indispensable role in enhancing research productivity of postgraduate students in private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria. The study established that serial resources such as journals, abstracts, theses, conference proceedings, annual reports, e-book collections, and newspapers are generally available across all the selected private universities, and are well utilised by postgraduate students. Effective utilisation of serials contributes positively to research productivity by improving access to current scholarly information, enhancing research quality, increasing publication output, promoting collaboration, and improving academic visibility. Despite the challenges inherent in utilisation of serial resources, the study affirmed that serial publications remain indispensable tools for postgraduate research and scholarly development in private universities.

7. Recommendations

1. To address the identified issues, private university libraries in North Central, Nigeria should diversify the available serial resources that align with postgraduate students' needs and preferences.

2. University management and library administration should improve access to serial resources through adequate funding, ICT facilities, and user education programs that will enhance effective serial resources utilisation for research productivity.
3. University libraries could promote their availability or integrate newspapers into information literacy programmes.

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